

EFFECTIVENESS OF CONDUCTING EXTRACURRICULAR ACTIVITIES IN VOLLEYBALL

Abduraxmonov Xayrullo Xakimjanovich

Faculty of Physical Culture

teacher of the department of theory of physical education

Jabaraliyev Bekzodjon To'qinjon

student of the faculty of physical culture

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11259612>

Annotation

The organizational basis for planning and conducting training sessions in the volleyball section has been determined. The peculiarities of the organization and content of extracurricular volleyball classes have been studied. The main orientation of the weekly cycle of training sessions aimed at consolidating and improving technical and tactical actions with parallel exercises for general physical training in a combined form of classes has been determined

Key words

Extracurricular activities, volleyball, age characteristics, forms of education, means of physical education

According to Yu.D. Zheleznyak, among the wide variety of means of solving the problem of improving the health of students at school, the game of volleyball occupies an important place. This is explained not only by its accessibility and aesthetic beauty, but also by its beneficial effect on the development of vital qualities, and above all the basic properties of attention (intensity, stability, switching), which is of exceptional importance at school age [6]. M.V. Astakhov, V.F. Strelchenko, D.P. Krakhmalev claim that playing volleyball develops the ability to quickly perform motor actions, jump high, instantly change direction and speed of movement, have dexterity and endurance [1].

At the same time, the issues of organizing extracurricular activities in volleyball for high school girls remain relevant at the moment. I.V. Orlan, argues that the organization and methodology of teaching sports games in physical education classes in secondary schools requires special attention, taking into account a number of factors. N.N. Kuindji noted that the gender approach to learning and the upbringing of children in school, its physiological, hygienic and social aspects are crucial.

In this regard, the problem of organizing extracurricular volleyball classes for girls of high school age is relevant. The peculiarities of the organization and content of extracurricular volleyball classes in the educational process in the

system of extracurricular work in the physical culture and sports field in a secondary school represent a specially organized activity of the teacher and students aimed at solving the problems of education, upbringing and personal development. The organization of activities for additional education of children should primarily be based on the form and objectives of the process.

According to Astaxov M.V., Strelchenko V.F., Kraxmalev D.P., the organization of a volleyball training session includes:

1. Knowledge of the contingent of students (gender, number, age), their level of physical, technical, tactical and mental preparedness, individual characteristics for choosing the optimal means and methods.

2. Consideration of motivation to practice volleyball for the choice of pedagogical teaching methods.

3. Completing and accounting for the material and technical support of classes.

4. The expediency of placing and moving, building, rebuilding, transitions of students, taking into account the solution of a specific task.

5. Forms of organization of educational activities:

a) simultaneous: frontal, group, individual.

b) alternate: circular, shift, alternate, in-line, alternating in pairs.

6. Organization of the work of assistants: on duty, judges, captains.

7. Organization of persons present at the lesson (temporarily released): listen, explain, analyze, answer teacher's questions, partially perform exercises [1]. As a practical material, we have developed the content of activities for the organization of training sessions for a week-long microcycle in the volleyball section of the university.

The material on the methodology and organization of physical culture and recreation work is based on the works of many authors, in particular I.V. Kalashnikov, L.A. Boyarskaya. The main focus of the week-long training sessions is aimed at consolidating and improving technical and tactical actions with parallel exercises for general physical training in a combined form of classes.

1. The organization of a combined form of classes consists in the fact that several subgroups perform various tasks. In particular, our experimental group of 12 pupils was divided into 4 subgroups, with 3 students each. The first subgroup consolidated the skills of the second gear at the grid, located in zones 4, 3 and 2. The second subgroup consolidated and improved the skills of receiving the ball from below. The third subgroup consolidated the attacking strike skills. The fourth subgroup performed acrobatic exercises.

2. Organization of the implementation of additional means of general physical training in the volleyball section. During classes, it is advisable to teach girls elementary basketball and handball techniques at the expense of the time allocated for general physical training. In the classroom, according to the recommendation of teachers, a wide variety of outdoor games, relay races, games preparatory to sports were necessarily used.

3. Organization of classes on the study of volleyball techniques, taking into account the general methodological rules for physical education lessons.

4. The organization of students in the performance of tasks. The use of inventory and equipment plays an important role here. To successfully conduct volleyball classes, it is absolutely not enough to have only a few volleyball balls and a net, a playground.

5. The use of front-group and conjugate methods. All students should participate in the exercises equally. To do this, the frontal method should be combined with the division of students into groups that perform various tasks: some performed tasks at the net with a volleyball ball, others performed exercises with stuffed balls, with a volleyball at the wall, with a ball for the development of motor coordination abilities.

6. Organization of theoretical and methodological training. We used conversations, a story, a lecture, and a survey as forms of a verbal method of physical education. The organization of the volleyball section included the development of questions using an active learning method. We used the active method of teaching in the form of a conversation with girls.

7. Organization of control tests. To do this, they organized control tests for general and special physical training, control volleyball games, performing certain technical and tactical tasks, hitting a target in a certain area of the court (for example, serving), the maximum number of receiving and passing the ball in a certain way with a partner.

8. Organization of game tasks and game techniques. When organizing classes, we paid special attention to the use of outdoor games. Given the uneven (different) level of preparedness of girls in volleyball, this method allowed them not to lose interest in the game, increased the emotional level of the lesson, and also allowed them to consolidate the skills and abilities of volleyball. The games helped to create a team. The collective beginning of outdoor games also forms positive character traits of schoolchildren, increases the level of their moral qualities.

9. Identification of assistants among students during training sessions. In the process of organizing classes, the need to include students themselves in the process as assistant instructors should be taken into account. This is necessary, first of all, in order to relieve the teacher and give him the opportunity to concentrate on certain groups, students, tasks, etc. It is also important for teaching students the basics of the methodology of conducting training sessions. The girls in our classes conducted general preparatory and special preparatory warm-up exercises, helped in accepting control standards and test tasks, monitored the technique of performing motor actions (the most prepared), supervised technical and tactical tasks, refereed control training games.

Thus, the peculiarities of the organization and content of extracurricular volleyball classes for grades 10-11 consist in planning and implementing the tasks of educational and cognitive activity based on the application of the organizational structure of the collective method of learning, which includes independent work, individual-frontal, collective-frontal, collective-group (unified and differentiated) forms of learning and mutual learning in its content. pairs of replacement personnel. The organization and content of classes are presented in this study by a number of points that allow us to determine the pedagogical conditions for the successful assimilation and improvement of the game of volleyball.

The features of the organization and content of classes in the volleyball section for girls of high school age are determined, which are presented in the form of nine points in accordance with the chosen topic of the weekly training microcycle. These organizational aspects were implemented in practice among high school students at the volleyball section in secondary schools of the city under the guidance of experienced physical education teachers.

An important feature in the organization of the volleyball section is the implementation of comprehensive control and correction of motor actions, which allows you to quickly assess technical readiness, the ability to manage your actions and the level of special physical fitness, ensuring the successful development of program training material. The survey as a means of problem-based learning is a complex of pedagogical diagnostics of learning effectiveness, consisting of blocks for assessing theoretical preparedness, for example, questions on the basics of techniques in volleyball, techniques for performing basic motor actions in volleyball, evaluating the ability to differentiate one's motor actions in special motor tests and a block for testing the level of

development of basic physical qualities that ensure technical actions in volleyball

The organizational basis for planning and conducting training sessions in the volleyball section has been determined. The peculiarities of the organization and content of extracurricular volleyball classes have been studied. The main orientation of the weekly cycle of training sessions aimed at consolidating and improving technical and tactical actions with parallel exercises for general physical training in a combined form of classes has been determined

Key words

Extracurricular activities, volleyball, age characteristics, forms of education, means of physical education

According to Yu.D. Zheleznyak, among the wide variety of means of solving the problem of improving the health of students at school, the game of volleyball occupies an important place. This is explained not only by its accessibility and aesthetic beauty, but also by its beneficial effect on the development of vital qualities, and above all the basic properties of attention (intensity, stability, switching), which is of exceptional importance at school age [6]. M.V. Astakhov, V.F. Strelchenko, D.P. Krakhmalev claim that playing volleyball develops the ability to quickly perform motor actions, jump high, instantly change direction and speed of movement, have dexterity and endurance [1].

At the same time, the issues of organizing extracurricular activities in volleyball for high school girls remain relevant at the moment. I.V. Orlan, argues that the organization and methodology of teaching sports games in physical education classes in secondary schools requires special attention, taking into account a number of factors. N.N. Kuindji noted that the gender approach to learning and the upbringing of children in school, its physiological, hygienic and social aspects are crucial.

In this regard, the problem of organizing extracurricular volleyball classes for girls of high school age is relevant. The peculiarities of the organization and content of extracurricular volleyball classes in the educational process in the system of extracurricular work in the physical culture and sports field in a secondary school represent a specially organized activity of the teacher and students aimed at solving the problems of education, upbringing and personal development. The organization of activities for additional education of children should primarily be based on the form and objectives of the process.

According to Astaxov M.V., Strelchenko V.F., Kraxmalev D.P., the organization of a volleyball training session includes:

1. Knowledge of the contingent of students (gender, number, age), their level of physical, technical, tactical and mental preparedness, individual characteristics for choosing the optimal means and methods.
2. Consideration of motivation to practice volleyball for the choice of pedagogical teaching methods.
3. Completing and accounting for the material and technical support of classes.
4. The expediency of placing and moving, building, rebuilding, transitions of students, taking into account the solution of a specific task.
5. Forms of organization of educational activities:
 - a) simultaneous: frontal, group, individual.
 - b) alternate: circular, shift, alternate, in-line, alternating in pairs.
6. Organization of the work of assistants: on duty, judges, captains.
7. Organization of persons present at the lesson (temporarily released): listen, explain, analyze, answer teacher's questions, partially perform exercises [1]. As a practical material, we have developed the content of activities for the organization of training sessions for a week-long microcycle in the volleyball section of the university.

The material on the methodology and organization of physical culture and recreation work is based on the works of many authors, in particular I.V. Kalashnikov, L.A. Boyarskaya. The main focus of the week-long training sessions is aimed at consolidating and improving technical and tactical actions with parallel exercises for general physical training in a combined form of classes.

1. The organization of a combined form of classes consists in the fact that several subgroups perform various tasks. In particular, our experimental group of 12 pupils was divided into 4 subgroups, with 3 students each. The first subgroup consolidated the skills of the second gear at the grid, located in zones 4, 3 and 2. The second subgroup consolidated and improved the skills of receiving the ball from below. The third subgroup consolidated the attacking strike skills. The fourth subgroup performed acrobatic exercises.
2. Organization of the implementation of additional means of general physical training in the volleyball section. During classes, it is advisable to teach girls elementary basketball and handball techniques at the expense of the time allocated for general physical training. In the classroom, according to the

recommendation of teachers, a wide variety of outdoor games, relay races, games preparatory to sports were necessarily used.

3. Organization of classes on the study of volleyball techniques, taking into account the general methodological rules for physical education lessons.

4. The organization of students in the performance of tasks. The use of inventory and equipment plays an important role here. To successfully conduct volleyball classes, it is absolutely not enough to have only a few volleyball balls and a net, a playground.

5. The use of front-group and conjugate methods. All students should participate in the exercises equally. To do this, the frontal method should be combined with the division of students into groups that perform various tasks: some performed tasks at the net with a volleyball ball, others performed exercises with stuffed balls, with a volleyball at the wall, with a ball for the development of motor coordination abilities.

6. Organization of theoretical and methodological training. We used conversations, a story, a lecture, and a survey as forms of a verbal method of physical education. The organization of the volleyball section included the development of questions using an active learning method. We used the active method of teaching in the form of a conversation with girls.

7. Organization of control tests. To do this, they organized control tests for general and special physical training, control volleyball games, performing certain technical and tactical tasks, hitting a target in a certain area of the court (for example, serving), the maximum number of receiving and passing the ball in a certain way with a partner.

8. Organization of game tasks and game techniques. When organizing classes, we paid special attention to the use of outdoor games. Given the uneven (different) level of preparedness of girls in volleyball, this method allowed them not to lose interest in the game, increased the emotional level of the lesson, and also allowed them to consolidate the skills and abilities of volleyball. The games helped to create a team. The collective beginning of outdoor games also forms positive character traits of schoolchildren, increases the level of their moral qualities.

9. Identification of assistants among students during training sessions. In the process of organizing classes, the need to include students themselves in the process as assistant instructors should be taken into account. This is necessary, first of all, in order to relieve the teacher and give him the opportunity to concentrate on certain groups, students, tasks, etc. It is also important for

teaching students the basics of the methodology of conducting training sessions. The girls in our classes conducted general preparatory and special preparatory warm-up exercises, helped in accepting control standards and test tasks, monitored the technique of performing motor actions (the most prepared), supervised technical and tactical tasks, refereed control training games.

Thus, the peculiarities of the organization and content of extracurricular volleyball classes for grades 10-11 consist in planning and implementing the tasks of educational and cognitive activity based on the application of the organizational structure of the collective method of learning, which includes independent work, individual-frontal, collective-frontal, collective-group (unified and differentiated) forms of learning and mutual learning in its content. pairs of replacement personnel. The organization and content of classes are presented in this study by a number of points that allow us to determine the pedagogical conditions for the successful assimilation and improvement of the game of volleyball.

The features of the organization and content of classes in the volleyball section for girls of high school age are determined, which are presented in the form of nine points in accordance with the chosen topic of the weekly training microcycle. These organizational aspects were implemented in practice among high school students at the volleyball section in secondary schools of the city under the guidance of experienced physical education teachers.

An important feature in the organization of the volleyball section is the implementation of comprehensive control and correction of motor actions, which allows you to quickly assess technical readiness, the ability to manage your actions and the level of special physical fitness, ensuring the successful development of program training material. The survey as a means of problem-based learning is a complex of pedagogical diagnostics of learning effectiveness, consisting of blocks for assessing theoretical preparedness, for example, questions on the basics of techniques in volleyball, techniques for performing basic motor actions in volleyball, evaluating the ability to differentiate one's motor actions in special motor tests and a block for testing the level of development of basic physical qualities that ensure technical actions in volleyball

Literature:

1. Астахова, М.В. Волейбол: учебно-методическое пособие по дисциплине «Физическая культура (элективный курс)» для студентов очной и заочной форм обучения по всем направлениям подготовки бакалавров / М.В.

- Астахова, В.Ф. Стрельченко, Д.П. Крахмалев. – Пятигорск: СКФУ, 2014. – 114 с. – ISBN 978-5-600-00812-0. – Текст: непосредственный
- 2.Басманова, Е.С. Гендерные особенности детей в организации образовательного процесса / Е.С. Басманова. – Текст: непосредственный // Молодой ученый. – 2014. – № 17. – С. 565-567.
- 3.Khakimzhonovich, A. K. (2022). THE ROLE OF A PHYSICAL EDUCATION TEACHER IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF SPEED AND STRENGTH QUALITIES OF SCHOOLCHILDREN-ATHLETES. *Academica Globe: Inderscience Research*, 3(11), 187-193.
4. Shohista, Q., & Xokimjonovich, A. X. (2022). Ways of using modern information technology opportunities in teaching sport psychology. *Uzbek Scholar Journal*, 8, 85-89.
5. Khakimzhonovich, A. K. (2022). THE ROLE OF A PHYSICAL EDUCATION TEACHER IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF SPEED AND STRENGTH QUALITIES OF SCHOOLCHILDREN-ATHLETES. *Academica Globe: Inderscience Research*, 3(11), 187-193.
6. Umirov, S. (2022). PROFESSIONAL SPORTDA YUQORI NATIJALARNI BASHORAT QILISHDA IRSIY VA ORTTIRMA OMILLARNING AHAMIYATI. *Евразийский журнал академических исследований*, 2(12), 100-103.
7. Umirov, S. B. (2023). NATIONAL STRUGGLE AS ONE OF THE TYPES OF PHYSICAL CULTURE. *American Journal of Pedagogical and Educational Research*, 18, 133-137.
8. Umirov, S. (2023). О 'QUVCHILARNI DARSDAN TASHQARI MASHG 'ULOTLARDA QO 'L TO 'PI SPORT TURIGA O 'RGATISHNING O 'ZIGA XOS XUSUSIYATI. *Центральноазиатский журнал образования и инноваций*, 2(6 Part 6), 26-33.
9. Khasanov, A. T., Kurbanov, G. R., & Mamatov, U. E. (2022). Experimental substantiation of efficiency accented physical education classes students of the faculty of "Military education". *INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF RESEARCH IN COMMERCE, IT, ENGINEERING AND SOCIAL SCIENCES* ISSN: 2349-7793 Impact Factor: 6.876, 16(10), 157-164.
10. Hasanov, A. (2022). Primary school students training movement games in physical education classes: primary school students training movement games in physical education classes. *Физическое воспитание, спорт и здоровье*, 2(2).
- 11.Khasanov, A. T., Kurbanov, G. R., & Mamatov, U. E. (2022). Experimental substantiation of efficiency accented physical education classes students of the faculty of "Military education". *INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF RESEARCH IN*

COMMERCE, IT, ENGINEERING AND SOCIAL SCIENCES ISSN: 2349-7793 Impact Factor: 6.876, 16(10), 157-164.

12. Хасанов, А. Т., & Азимов, А. М. (2022). МЕТОДИЧЕСКИЕ ПОДХОДЫ К РАЗРАБОТКЕ ПРОФЕССИОГРАММЫ УЧИТЕЛЯ ФИЗИЧЕСКОЙ КУЛЬТУРЫ. ИЖОДКОР О'QITUVCHИ, 2(24), 449-455.

